

Habits of Mind for Entrepreneurship Education

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ABSTRACT: Entrepreneurship education is vital to ameliorate the high youth unemployment rate in South Africa. As part of efforts to augment entrepreneurship education, purposeful teacher training is needed. Integral in this pursuit is the amendment and development of teachers' entrepreneurial mindset. The concept of 'mindset' is, however, ambiguous, as literature uses this term interchangeably with concepts such as 21st century skills, soft skills, non-cognitive skills, or character strengths. When a new teacher training program for entrepreneurship education was being developed, it was necessary to investigate and analyze all these skills or characteristics, to ascertain which aspects should be included in the program to contribute to the entrepreneurial mindset that was envisioned for these teachers. An exploratory qualitative literature review was conducted from a constructivist point of view. Accessible literature on 'entrepreneurship education' and 'entrepreneurial mindset' was systematically and thematically analyzed to explore the contribution of various types of skills and characteristics to the construction of an entrepreneurial mindset, in preparation for entrepreneurship education. The findings revealed that several skills, characteristics and habits contribute to the development of positive entrepreneurial mindsets. These included several references to the 'Habits of Mind' proposed by Costa and Kallick (2008). Subsequent comprehensive analysis was conducted to explore the pertinence of the Habits of Mind for developing teachers' entrepreneurial mindsets as part of their preparation to facilitate entrepreneurship education. A recommendation was made for the inclusion of all the Habits of Mind to contribute to fostering positive entrepreneurial mindsets as part of teacher training for entrepreneurship education.

KEYWORDS: 21st century skills, entrepreneurial mindset, entrepreneurship education, habits of mind, teacher training

Background and problem statement

Youth unemployment is a growing concern globally, but especially in South Africa, where the youth unemployment rate escalated to 59 percent in the first quarter of 2020 (Trading Economics 2020). The potential of entrepreneurship education to ameliorate the high unemployment levels in this country is thus clear. At present, entrepreneurship education in the curriculum used in South African schools is limited (Du Toit and Kempen 2018), which prompted the Department of Basic Education to compile a blueprint for expanding entrepreneurship education to amend this gap (Department of Basic Education [DBE] 2016). The 'Blueprint for Entrepreneurship Education' document includes four key recommendations to bridge the current gap (DBE 2016, 9), the third of which recommends training teachers – both pre-service and in-service – with the explicit purpose of enabling them to develop their learners' entrepreneurship education effectively.

At one of the foremost universities in South Africa, a few detached strategies had already been employed to prepare teachers for entrepreneurship education. However, the DBE's renewed focus on and drive to implement entrepreneurship education inspired a number of lecturers at this university's Faculty of Education to join forces to reconsider and redesign a new teacher training program that would contribute to improved teacher training for entrepreneurship education in South Africa, in line with the requirements of the DBE (2016, 11). The teacher training program would have to be suitable for both pre-service and in-service teachers, to enable the dissemination of effective entrepreneurship education to as many learners as possible.

Training teachers for entrepreneurship education however entails much more than developing knowledge and requires a different way of thinking and acting (Paloniemi and Belt 2015). As a point of departure, the statement by Seif, Kallick and Costa (2011, 1), that “teacher improvement and greater effectiveness are not determined by genetics, but by whether or not a teacher has key qualities and positive attitudes – Habits of Mind – that create the willingness and motivation to put in the required effort to improve teaching skills over time” was therefore acknowledged. Furthermore, the declaration of Nadelson et al. (2018, 114) that instruction and support is needed to foster a preferred entrepreneurial mindset “that embraces, processes and acts upon ideas of entrepreneurship”, was endorsed. The amendment and development of teachers’ entrepreneurial mindset should thus form the foundation and would be integral in the new teacher training program. The concept of ‘mindset’ is, however, fluid and sometimes ambiguous. For example, Claxton, Costa and Kallick (2016, 60) use the term mindset interchangeably with concepts such as 21st century skills, soft skills, non-cognitive skills, or character strengths. In another example, Toutain and Fayolle (2017, 989) define an entrepreneurial mindset as “the acquisition of a dynamic set of attitudes, values and cross-disciplinary competencies... [relying] mostly on the acquisition of soft skills ...” According to the Online Etymology Dictionary (2020), the term ‘mindset’ was initially used by psychologists and educators around 1916 and referred to “habits of mind formed by previous experience”. Based on these examples from literature, a mindset can thus be viewed as a way of thinking that can be taught and developed, and which depends on the prior experiences of learners (or, in this case, teachers-as-learners), as well as on them developing several skills or competencies. Thus, as part of the planning of and development for the new teacher training program for entrepreneurship education, it was necessary to investigate and analyze the different ways of thinking, as well as skills or characteristics, to ascertain which of these aspects should be included in the program to contribute to the entrepreneurial mindset that was envisioned for these South African teachers. The problem was that the large number of ways of thinking, skills and competencies associated with developing an entrepreneurial mindset, had to be refined to determine which of these aspects were vital for inclusion in the new teacher training program. The overarching goal of this investigation was to contribute to improved teacher training for entrepreneurship education, as per the DBE directive. The question that guided this investigation was ‘How can an entrepreneurial mindset be developed as part of teacher training for entrepreneurship education?’

Conceptual and theoretical framework

Four key concepts created the framework used for the investigation, specifically ‘ways of thinking’; ‘prior experiences’; ‘skills’ and ‘competencies’. These concepts emerged from the initial literature review as key contributors to developing preferred mindsets. The current investigation explored how the entrepreneurial mindset of teachers could be developed, to inform the structuring of the new teacher training program for entrepreneurship education.

‘Ways of thinking’ refers to how teachers and teachers-in-training think about or view entrepreneurship. Preconceived (and sometimes narrow) notions of teachers could influence their approach to teaching entrepreneurship education negatively. This will also be the case if teachers are not well-informed about the benefits and value of entrepreneurship education for their learners. Paloniemi and Belt (2015, 265) noted that entrepreneurship education should be viewed as “a valid concept in all human activities”, rather than narrowly focusing on “entrepreneurship as business-related functions and entrepreneurs as opportunity discoverers”, a view that many teachers share (p. 269). For this reason, the World Economic Forum recommends the creation of environments that will be conducive to encouraging entrepreneurial ways of thinking (WEF 2009).

Teachers’ prior experiences will impact the way they think about entrepreneurship as well as their knowledge about and frame of reference for teaching entrepreneurship education. A lack of prior entrepreneurship experience may limit the development of entrepreneurial characteristics (Ramayah, Ahmad and Fei 2012). In a suggestion that may overcome this issue, Kurczewska

(2016) combines prior experiences and prior learning, referring to this aspect as ‘the learning history’, which allows learners (teachers-as-learners in the current study) to reflect on past learning and experiences, learn from those, and plan for similar future incidences. Although prior experience may influence mindset, a preferred mindset can also be effectively developed through teaching and learning (Nadelson et al. 2018). Toutain and Fayolle (2017) recommend that a more open approach – to transform learners and learning – rather than a closed, prescriptive pedagogical approach, should be used for effective entrepreneurship education. The European Union (EU) recommends “Competence oriented [teaching-learning] approaches such as project based, arts based, inquiry based, experiential or work-based learning, [to] improve learning outcomes and learner engagement” (EU 2019, 15), all of which are also valid for entrepreneurship education. The European Union further notes that such education should include “opportunities for innovation, collaboration and cross-discipline learning”, should place learners at the center of the learning process, and should require learners’ active participation in their own learning (EU 2019, 15). Plans for new teacher training programs should therefore consider teachers’ prior experiences of teaching-learning methodologies, and include preparation to support teachers in developing new insights and experiences that are aligned with preferred teaching-learning strategies for entrepreneurship education.

Skills are the abilities of individuals to utilize prior and new knowledge while carrying out processes, in order to achieve results (EU 2019). While skill depends primarily on learning, it also covers the principles of performance efficiency and effectiveness (Adeyemo 2009). In particular, entrepreneurial skills include a variety of practices, activities and “know-how” which have to be taught to enable learners to become effective entrepreneurs (Mamun, Fazal, and Muniady 2019, 31). Entrepreneurial skills include both ‘hard skills’ (such as designing a marketing plan) and ‘soft skills’ (such as critical thinking or problem-solving) (Kakouris and Morselli 2020). Cataloguing and refining these particular skills were, however, not the core focus of the current investigation. What was important to note, was that these skills can be taught (Nadelson et al. 2018), as well as the assertion of Mamun et al. (2019) that learners have to develop a set of skills (through teaching and learning) that would underpin new ways of thinking, as well as the competencies they need to become efficient entrepreneurs. These skills were therefore included in the teacher training program, so that trained teachers could transfer similar skills to learners in their classes.

Competencies (the fourth key concept) are based on a combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes that is developed throughout a learners’ life, in both formal and informal educational settings (EU 2019). In the current study, competencies were viewed as abilities or capabilities required of an individual to perform or complete a task competently. Entrepreneurship competence is one of eight key competencies for learners in the European Union and refers to the “capacity to act upon opportunities and ideas, and to transform them into value for others” (2019, 19). This competence, therefore, envisages that learners will be taught how to combine knowledge, skills and attitudes to create entrepreneurial value not only for themselves, but also to the benefit of others. Entrepreneurship education can contribute financial, creative, social and ecological value (to name but a few) and should not narrowly focus on only developing financial or economic value (Rae 2010). Teachers’ ability and capability (or their competence) to effectively teach and foster learners’ competencies to create entrepreneurial value in different fields, therefore need to be enhanced in teacher training programs for entrepreneurship education.

Teachers need to develop all four of these concepts (ways of thinking, prior experiences, skills and competencies) to support the effectiveness of teaching entrepreneurship education. In other words, each of these concepts contributes to the construction and development of a positive entrepreneurial mindset. For this reason, the research was approached using a constructivist lens. From a constructivist viewpoint, an entrepreneurial mindset can be constructed through developing or fostering certain ways of thinking, skills and competencies, as well as through analyzing and adding to prior knowledge. Furthermore, teachers must have a positive

entrepreneurial mindset in order for them to learn about entrepreneurship (themselves) and to appreciate the value of entrepreneurship education, but also to enable them to construct effective entrepreneurship education experiences for their learners. Programs for teacher training, therefore have to develop a different way of thinking – which will influence how teachers view entrepreneurship education, and how they make meaning of knowledge as part of entrepreneurship education. To change their mindset (way of thinking) to increasingly view entrepreneurship as valuable learning for every learner – and not only for those learners who choose to become entrepreneurs.

Empirical investigation

An exploratory qualitative literature review was conducted from a constructivist point of view. Desktop research was used to find published research that would contribute to the purpose of the research, which was to explore the contribution of various ways of thinking, skills and characteristics to the construction of an entrepreneurial mindset, as part of entrepreneurship education. The key terms ‘entrepreneurship education’ and ‘entrepreneurial mindset’ were used for the search. The resources of the university library and the search engines it subscribes to were utilized. In particular, EBSCO-host were used, as the focus of the investigation centered on education, teaching and learning. Initially, the searches only extended to articles from the last decade, but as the analysis progressed, older publications that were referenced frequently in newer publications (such as the 2008 Habits of Mind book by Costa and Kallick) were also included in the analysis. The data were analyzed by means of systematic thematic analysis. The focus was on the *a-priori* codes of ‘ways of thinking’; ‘prior experiences’; ‘skills’ and ‘competencies’ that were determined from the initial literature review. Initially, many aspects related to each of these four concepts were identified as having the potential to contribute to answering the research question. However, after categorizing the codes and refinement of the themes, one particular aspect – the Habits of Mind – was identified as recurring in literature to a much greater extent than others. A second tier of analysis of the literature with a particular focus on how the Habits of Mind could affect the development of teachers’ mindset in the training program for entrepreneurship education, was subsequently conducted. The interpretation of the data was informed by how each of the habits realizes in or contribute to developing a positive entrepreneurial mindset, which were used to develop recommendations for inclusion in the teacher training program for entrepreneurship education.

Findings and discussion

The analysis of the data from the exploratory qualitative literature review revealed a vast amount of aspects that could contribute to or affect the development of a positive entrepreneurial mindset. Data analysis resulted in two themes that recurred most often in the literature, namely (1) that entrepreneurship education has to be structured to support learners to excel in today's educational climate (but which was not the core focus of the current study), and (2) that teachers need a wide array of entrepreneurial skills to enable them to teach entrepreneurship education effectively. It also emerged that the current set of essential skills or competencies suggested by the EU for its learners to enable them to excel in current learning climates (EU 2019, 13), align closely to the Habits of Mind that were developed by Costa and Kallick (2008).

Habits of Mind is based on a process that involves mindful thinking (Costa and Kallick 2008, xii), which increases learners’ eagerness to act with intellect when faced with problems, and may lead to answers that are not immediately apparent (p. 16). When humans encounter dichotomies, are puzzled by dilemmas, or face uncertainties, their most successful actions require specific patterns of rational activity to be drawn out. When drawing on these intellectual resources, the results that are produced through them are more powerful, of higher quality, and considerably more significant than when failing to use these patterns of intellectualism. The intellectual resources for successful behaviors require the development and maintenance of

certain habits of intellectual behavior, or Habits of Mind. Developing and subsequently employing Habits of Mind requires a combination of various, attitudes, skills and past experiences. It requires that one thinking pattern is valued more than another, and implies intentionally choosing which habit should be used at which time. In addition, sensitivity to contextual indications in a situation that indicates that it is a suitable time and circumstance to employ a pattern, is needed (Costa and Kallick 2008). Thus, it became clear that the different, intentional way of thinking associated with the Habits of Mind were closely aligned to what was required to be included in the new teacher training program for entrepreneurship education. However, uncertainty existed about the suitability of including all sixteen of the Habits of Mind (Costa and Kallick 2008) for developing teachers' entrepreneurial mindset to teach entrepreneurship education effectively. Therefore the remainder of the investigation focused solely on analyzing the suitability of each of the sixteen Habits of Mind for their potential contribution to support an entrepreneurial mindset when teaching entrepreneurship education.

Persisting

Persistence is a way of thinking teachers need for entrepreneurship education to enable them to cultivate the same habit of 'never give up' in their learners, to motivate learners to work with precision and to find ways to reach their goal when they think they are stuck (Seif et al. 2011). Teachers have to lay a foundation for persistence in entrepreneurship education that supports learners to concentrate on the task at hand, as well as to stick it out through distraction to ensure that the work gets done (Adeyemo 2009). In a continuously changing education environment, the researchers agree with Seif et al. (2011), that if teachers are trained to develop learners' skill of persisting, learners will be more motivated to overcome challenges and become self-confident, which can be transferred to entrepreneurship or contribute skills for employability.

Managing impulsivity

An efficient entrepreneur is one that is able to carefully and effectively manage time. Teachers also have to be successful managers of time and prioritize tasks efficiently. According to Costa and Kallick (2008, xx), managing impulsivity means "Take your time. Think before you act. Remain calm, thoughtful, and deliberate". It is therefore not a reference to working faster, but rather more determinedly and thoughtfully. To schedule and plan, teachers have to set their minds by thinking before acting, taking responsibility of the outcome of the thinking process, keeping calm if things do not work out as planned, be cautious, and take calculated risks when necessary (Costa and Kallick 2008). Impulsivity can, therefore, represent strength in entrepreneurial teaching – if it is managed well – and teachers need to be taught this skill.

Listening with understanding and empathy

Beall et al. (2008, 130) suggest that teachers should be "aware of listening and trained to be better listeners to begin making a difference in learners' listening competence". Learners' listening competence is therefore shaped by the example their teachers set on this front. It implies wisdom to seek out and listen to the advice of more knowledgeable others to contribute to knowledge construction, which is also supported in effective entrepreneurship education (European Commission 2011, 7) and evident of constructivism. Entrepreneurial competence "includes a desire to motivate others and value their ideas, empathy and taking care of people and the world, and accepting responsibility-taking ethical approaches throughout the process" (EU 2019, 13). Listening to and learning from others require the listener to "devote mental energy to another person's thoughts and ideas" (Costa and Kallick 2008, xx), which will expand knowledge as well as ways of thinking about or viewing concepts, and which will be beneficial in entrepreneurship. Teachers have to be taught how to listen deeply for their own teaching efficiency, and to enable them to transfer this skill.

Thinking flexibly

The willingness to adapt to change is a trait of teachers who have real entrepreneurial competence. It implies looking at situations in new ways, or finding ways to “change perspectives, generate alternatives, and consider options” (Costa and Kallick 2008, xxi). Teachers need to be keen on thinking about how to use the best teaching approach to meet the needs of their learners, but also adhere to the requirements for effective entrepreneurship education. This includes understanding the idea of adjusting their learners' view of the subject they teach to support an entrepreneurial mindset and to thinking flexibly. The teacher has to consider which teaching strategy will be the best approach to teach the content to the learners —challenging learners with a problem-based approach. The new teacher training program would therefore also incorporate this way of thinking.

Metacognition

Entrepreneurial skills include “constructive reflection within evolving creative processes and innovation” (EU 2019, 13). Thinking about ways of thinking and reflections combine to contribute to metacognition. Metacognition is an essential skill that all teachers have to learn. They have to become self-aware of their ways of thinking and their implementation of those thoughts, and they then have to reflect on the process – before, during and after the fact. They need to understand why they think about knowledge in a certain way, and how their way of thinking impacts all other aspects of their teaching. For example, teachers need to think which teaching approach will suit a specific topic the best and reflect for, during and after the teaching thereof, in order to improve subsequent lessons. The mindset of the teacher develops by practicing this habit, therefore metacognition and reflection will be vital for inclusion in the new teacher training program.

Striving for accuracy

The Habits of Mind concerned with analytic accuracy and precision are intimately connected to learners' “desire for exactness, fidelity, craftsmanship, and truth” (Costa and Kallick 2008, xxi). Learners who are striving for accuracy can figure things out, clarifying problems, gather data and recheck information (Adeyemo 2009). Entrepreneurs who strive to produce the most accurate product, or design the most accurate process or structure, will be better enabled to meet the needs of their customers. Costa and Kallick (2008) state that “flexible people are the ones with the most control” (p. 168), because they can shift their thinking and retain key information without losing their focus. Teachers therefore cannot have a slap-dash attitude toward teaching entrepreneurship education, and this competency will have to be instilled in them as part of their training program.

Questioning and problem posing

Problem-solving is embedded in and threaded through many of the key competencies for the future, according to the EU. “A problem-solving attitude supports both the learning process and the individual's ability to handle obstacles and change” (EU 2019, 11). Problem-solving relies on an ability to pose problems in the form of questions that need to be answered, but also on finding problems to solve (Costa and Kallick 2008). Kowalski (2009) addressed circumstances in which teachers and learners can benefit from the use of questions when he stated that “when teaching, the most powerful tool teachers have is the ability to engage the learner by asking questions. In general, learners tend to speak rather than listen. Asking questions facilitates talking” (p. 344). Teachers can use questions to engage learners in their own learning; to determine learners' prior knowledge, scaffold new knowledge and guide learners in the process to develop potential answers. Questioning allows both learners and teachers to explain their thinking, and challenge them to resolve problems, which is in line with the key competencies for the future of the EU (2019, 9), and also aligns well

with the requirements for effective entrepreneurship education. Teachers therefore have to be trained to develop the skills needed to pose useable questions and problems to their learners.

Applying past knowledge to new situations

Ștefănică et al. (2017, 855) indicate that subject-specific prior knowledge is the primary predictor for the development of professional competence. The habit of applying past or previously learned knowledge to new situations is essential for teachers developing an entrepreneurial mindset for effective entrepreneurship education. Ko and Butler (2007, 366) suggest that an ability to link previously unassociated information to derive new combinations is potentially useful for enabling “entrepreneurs and learners to be more creative in ways that make entrepreneurial behavior more likely”. According to the European Union (2019, 11) “the desire to apply prior learning and life experiences and the curiosity to look for opportunities to learn and develop in a variety of life contexts” contribute to personal, social and learning competencies. Teacher training should contribute to teachers’ competence to effectively construct new knowledge based on existing or prior knowledge of learners, so as to contribute to a broader learning experience for learners.

Thinking and communicating with clarity and precision

One of the primary dispositions of a teacher is communicating efficiently with colleagues, parents and learners, interacting with accuracy and consistency. Clear and precise communication ensures that information is not lost between parties and contributes to better understanding between different individuals. Without effective communication among stakeholders, learning becomes less structured and effective (Seif et al. 2011) and this therefore is a crucial skill every teacher should practice to enhance effective communication and collaboration with all stakeholders. According to the EU “Individuals should have the skills to communicate both orally and in writing in a variety of situations and monitor and adapt their own communication to the requirements of the situation” (EU 2019, 6). They should also develop the ability to “communicate constructively in different environments, collaborate in teams and negotiate” (EU 2019, 11). Communication is embedded in and threaded through most of the key competencies for the future, making it vital for inclusion in the teacher training program for entrepreneurship education.

Gather data through all senses

Most learning relies on auditory and visual senses of learners. Hearing and sight is often viewed as the gateway to learning. However, this narrow view excludes several other senses that can contribute to learners’ learning and understanding, such as olfactory (smell), tactile (touch), or kinesthetic (movement) senses (Costa and Kallick 2008). These other senses can be used to collect data (knowledge and understanding) that will contribute to a much richer learning experience for learners. In the modern educational world learners also have to learn how to identify, evaluate and select digital data, a competency referred to as digital literacy (EU 2019, 10). The outdated belief that learning is ‘only linked to books’ need to be shelved and teachers have to be trained to use more of their senses to collect data, as well as other resources, including digital data sources, that will contribute to a broader and richer learning experience for their learners.

Creating, imagining and innovating

“A positive attitude includes curiosity about the world, an openness to imagine new possibilities...” (EU 2019, 14). Creative thinking needs to be developed as part of entrepreneurship education in order to foster different ways of thinking that will enable new ideas and new solutions to existing problems. Generating new and innovative methods and solutions are key ways of thinking to support teachers to create positive entrepreneurial mindsets. Creativity is a skill that is included in several of the key

competencies that learners will need in the future (EU 2019, 10). In addition, “Entrepreneurial skills are founded on creativity ...” (EU 2019, 13), thus creativity, imagination and innovation are foundational skills that are required for entrepreneurship, and these should be included in entrepreneurship education. The innovative and creative ways of thinking should be taught to teachers, so that they can transfer similar learning to their learners.

Responding with wonderment and awe

According to Eisner (1991, 11), “One important aim of schooling should be to create a climate that evokes learners’ sense of wonder and inspires their imaginations to soar”. He suggested that learners need to enjoy what they are learning in school so that they will want to continue learning outside of school. According to Eisner, “Intellectual activity at its highest level is often associated with play” (p. 14). Play gets learners involved so that they feel fulfilled and want to know more. One of Eisner’s priorities is that “In classrooms, it also counts to teach the youth the importance of wonder” (p. 15). He proposed that schools tend to “undermine the significance of wonder” (p. 15). Teachers tend to believe that they are not working while learners daydream. This aspect closely links to teachers’ choice of teaching-learning methods, thus, to support effective entrepreneurship education, teachers have to be trained in methods and pedagogies that will foster learners’ sense of wonderment and awe.

Taking responsible risks

“The ability to ... cope with uncertainty, ambiguity and risk as part of making informed decisions is essential” (EU 2019, 13). Teachers need to take responsible risks while considering many variables on a daily basis. This habit will let them change their entrepreneurial mindset and those of the learners. Teachers can try new pathways, become self-motivated and self-disciplined, but have to know when to stop if the risk becomes too high. Attempting new and innovative methods, even though the risk of failure exists, is essential to challenge learners and make the learning process awe-inspiring. Teachers are therefore urged to take chances and explore new teaching methods in their classrooms (Adeyemo 2009; Seif et al. 2011), but they have to be taught how to do this effectively.

Finding humor

According to Kuhrik et al. (1997, 333), humor helps teachers to create a “positive learning environment; laughter in the classroom signals [that] learners are learning”. In another study, Lei et al. (2010, 331) found that “the use of humor can also increase learners’ interest, attention, motivation, and comprehension of the course material”. Thus, when implementing humor as one of the Habits of Mind, learners will feel more comfortable and free to ask questions. Based on their own collective experiences, the researchers established that learners’ academic performance improves due to the openness between the lecturer and the learner created by including humor in teaching-learning. Despite links between humor and entrepreneurship education being nebulous, the positive effect that humor has on learning environments, underscores the need to also include this habit of mind in the training program to develop teachers’ positive mindset.

Thinking interdependently

Thinking interdependently benefits learners who work together in groups, are part of a team, or who collaborate to share ideas reciprocally (Costa and Kallick 2008). Learners “should be able to communicate constructively in different environments, collaborate in teams and negotiate” as part of personal, social and learning to learn competencies that are required for modern educational contexts (EU 2019, 11). The Oxford Dictionary (2020) defines ‘collaboration’ as “The action of working with someone to produce something” which clearly shows the value of this skill for entrepreneurship education. The reciprocal approach to interdependent thinking highlights that such thinking and the

resultant co-construction of knowledge benefits all parties involved and it is therefore not one-sided, which further motivates learners. Teachers have to be trained on the value of this way of thinking, as well as how to carefully construct this process as part of learning.

Remaining open to continuous learning

The illusion sometimes exist in teachers as well as learners that "I have so much more to experience" (Hayat 2019) which hinders their construction of new knowledge. Teachers should become life-long learners and be receptive for continuous learning (Hayat 2019). Habits of Mind is one of the five standards of Marzano's framework of life-long learning (Marzano et al. 1994), which is based on three aspects, i.e. self-regulation, critical thinking, and creative thinking. Being open to new learning also means being open to unlearning and re-learning, which is essential in the fast-changing educational landscape of the present. Continuous life-long learning will add to continued construction of knowledge, and development of skills and competencies, which can all serve in the pursuit of entrepreneurial opportunities. Teachers have to become lifelong learners, and continuously strive to improve their own learning, in order for their learners to benefit from their updated learning.

Conclusion and recommendation

Entrepreneurship education is vital to ameliorate the high youth unemployment rate in South Africa. To augment entrepreneurship education, purposeful teacher training is needed with a particular focus on amending and developing teachers' entrepreneurial mindset. It can be concluded that several skills, characteristics and habits contribute to the development of positive entrepreneurial mindsets, including each of the sixteen Habits of Mind. It is therefore recommended that the new teacher training program for entrepreneurship education be scaffolded around the sixteen habits that will contribute to developing the ways of thinking, skills and competencies of the teachers in the program. In addition, several of the Habits of Mind will support teachers in utilizing and/or adjusting their prior learning in order to be open to or contribute to the construction of new knowledge. If the new teacher training program is successful in training teachers for effective entrepreneurship education, more learners will take up entrepreneurship which in turn will contribute to ameliorating the high unemployment rate in South Africa.

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